

WHY

A webbased guideline 'One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses'

Zoonoses are a constant threat to human and animal health. A systematic cross-sectoral (One Health) approach to share signals, assess risks and coordinate the response is essential to minimise impact of zoonotic diseases.

Goal

Support countries to set up or strengthen One Health collaboration in the area of risk analysis (signalling, risk assessment, risk management, risk communication) of zoonoses including antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

Focus

Implementation and operationalisation of a One Health Risk Analysis System (OHRAS).

How

Stepwise approach to implement a OHRAS tailored to each country's situation and needs.

What

Organisation of risk analysis activities in a One Health fashion, such as signalling, risk assessment and risk management.

Who

Professionals involved in the risk analysis of zoonoses including AMR, who would like to make a change in the One Health collaboration within their country.

Included

Several barriers are addressed, such as the difficulty to obtain political will and to gain trust.

